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Comment on Channabasavaiah's Economic Statistics for Mining in India

Bell, Peter

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Abstract

Channabasavaiah and Naidu (2021) provide a useful summary of economic statistics on mining in India, based on several public sources at the national and state levels. They show how to aggregate information across sources to give a more accurate picture. This article presents additional calculations using their survey data in new ways. I present methods to estimate the labour share of income associated with mining and further discuss multiplier effects on GDP from mine workers' labour income. It is essential to coordinate data collection and disclosure across different levels of government to improve financial statistics and provide the best possible information to global audiences, especially as new funding models for infrastructure and mining projects emerge.

Keywords: Manganese and Iron ore production, Employment, and revenue generated by the mining sector, India, GDP Methodology, Labour Share, Labour Productivity, Resource Booms, Economic Development,

JEL Codes:

D19 - Other

D3 - Distribution

D33 - Factor Income Distribution

J4 - Particular Labour Markets

J8 - Labour Standards: National and International

J81 - Working Conditions

L7 - Industry Studies: Primary Products and Construction

L70 - General

N5 - Agriculture, Natural Resources, Environment, and Extractive Industries

N50 - General, International, or Comparative

O1 - Economic Development

Q32 - Exhaustible Resources and Economic Development

Q33 - Resource Booms

Q59 - Other

R1 - General Regional Economics

R52 - Land Use and Other Regulations

Y1 - Data: Tables and Charts

Y3 - Book Reviews (unclassified)

Comment on Channabasavaiah's Economic Statistics for Mining in India

Channabasavaiah and Naidu (2021) provide a useful summary of economic statistics on mining in India, based on several public sources at the national and state levels. National data include the Minerals Yearbook and the Economic Survey Report of India. Still, the Department of Mines and Geology for the state government of Karnataka and the district governments provide additional reports with relevant statistics to understand the economic impacts of mining at a high degree of resolution. This provides an example of how aggregating information across several sources can give a more accurate picture of economic activity. It is essential to coordinate data collection and disclosure across different levels of government to improve financial statistics and provide the best possible information to global audiences, especially as new funding models for infrastructure projects supporting businesses, such as mining, emerge.

The average daily employment and mining revenue are basic data points that can be useful for estimating direct impacts on GDP. However, the indirect effects on GDP can be modelled using the methods presented here. For comparison, the Government of Canada (2025) provides the following summary statistics for direct and indirect impact on GDP from mining: “... direct and indirect contribution of the minerals and metals sector accounted for 6% of Canada's total gross domestic product (GDP) in 2023. Indirect GDP for the minerals sector was \$42 billion, while direct GDP was \$117 billion. The direct contribution is further divided into mining and related support activities (\$63 billion) and minerals processing (\$53 billion).”

The definition of an indirect contribution to GDP is a valuable concept, and the Government of Canada (2025) provides further details, including upstream and downstream businesses and consumer channels. Another channel is where mine workers earn relatively high incomes and spend them quickly on things that lead to further local spending. How does the velocity of money for mine workers depend on their personal wealth or the average income in their area?

Channabasavaiah and Naidu (2021) provide data on annual mineral production in tonnes

and rupees. They also mention the state produces approximately 3,000kg of gold, but do not give any tonnage or employment statistics associated with gold mining. The article provides the number of people employed per day in iron ore and manganese mining in Karnataka, which is a relatively high-resolution data point. I calculate the ratio of total mineral value per year divided by the number of worker days per year: how much mineral value does each mine worker create each day? And how does the labour income of the mine worker compare with the government's tax share and other stakeholders? This article further explains these concepts and introduces a toy model of income to show how workers' spending can reverberate through the economy.

I calculate some basic statistics from the article (2021) to show the government's take.

Table 1	Number of Mines	Number of Workers	Average Number of Workers per Mine	Government Royalty (Rs. in crore)	Forex Rate USD/RUP	Government Royalty Total USD	Total Royalty per worker
Year	Table 2	Table 6	Calculated	Table 12	World Bank	Calculated	Calculated
2008-09	239	9953	42	Missing	0.021	Missing	Missing
2009-10	233	10261	44	Missing	0.022	Missing	Missing
2010-11	251	9664	39	Missing	0.023	Missing	Missing
2011-12	185	9918	54	1326.59	0.02	\$265,318,000	\$26,751
2012-13	219	8780	40	1485.48	0.017	\$252,531,600	\$28,762
2013-14	192	9339	49	658.84	0.016	\$105,414,400	\$11,288
2014-15	197	9332	47	1648.92	0.016	\$263,827,200	\$28,271
2015-16	160	9230	58	2003.61	0.015	\$300,541,500	\$32,561
2016-17	155	9242	60	2185.02	0.016	\$349,603,200	\$37,828
2017-18	137	9253	68	2746.26	0.015	\$411,939,000	\$44,520
2018-19		Missing		1496.56			

These calculations show government royalties range from \$25,000 to \$44,000 per mine worker per year. I calculate this by combining the royalties from Table 12 with the daily number of workers in Table 11, and assuming each person works 300 days per year. I consider this to be a very large value compared with GDP per capita.

The government taxes are structured as a production royalty. The Karnataka Legislative Assembly (2024) tax bill shows the baseline value is Rs 100 per tonne for Iron Ore (CLO, Lumps, fines, and concentrates, all grades), or approximately \$1 per tonne. Again, this may seem small, but it allows the government to take production royalties that range from \$100 million to \$400 million per year!

The data from Channabasavaiah and Naidu (2021) shows mining as a billion-dollar industry annually across approximately 100-200 mines in Karnataka, with around 10,000 people employed. With further exploratory data analysis of total tonnage for all mine production in the state of Karnataka from Table 2 (Channabasavaiah and Naidu, 2021), I find that the government's mining taxes through the production royalty range from 10% to 30% of the gross value of minerals produced from all mines in Karnataka each year.

Table 2	Total Tonnage All Mines	Gross Value All Metals (USD)	Metal Value per tonne mined	Government Royalty Total USD	Percent of Mineral Value paid as Royalty
Year	Table 2	Table 2	Calculated	Calculated	Calculated
2008-09	2,736,309	\$1,211,471,835	\$442.74	Missing	Missing
2009-10	2,768,107	\$1,335,577,870	\$482.49	Missing	Missing
2010-11	2,558,948	\$2,138,950,757	\$835.87	Missing	Missing
2011-12	245,463	\$893,484,700	\$3,640.00	\$265,318,000	30%
2012-13	2,339,490	\$1,034,844,145	\$442.34	\$252,531,600	24%
2013-14	2,345,439	\$1,261,239,056	\$537.74	\$105,414,400	8%
2014-15	2,416,452	\$1,234,526,528	\$510.88	\$263,827,200	21%
2015-16	781,196	\$837,739,395	\$1,072.38	\$300,541,500	36%
2016-17	909,619	\$1,011,987,056	\$1,112.54	\$349,603,200	35%
2017-18	912,845	\$1,439,424,960	\$1,576.86	\$411,939,000	29%
2018-19	Missing	Missing	Missing	\$209,518,400	Missing

The metals produced in Karnataka range from \$1 billion to \$2 billion overall. The total amount of rock mined ranges from 1 million to 2 million tonnes per year. However, it is unclear exactly how this quantity variable is defined in terms of the combination of iron ore and manganese ore. Using the figures provided, I find that the government's mining taxes through the production royalty range from 10% to 30% of the gross value of minerals produced from all mines in Karnataka each year.

For comparison, Mining Data Online notes that the Karnataka iron ore mines form part of Vedanta Limited's Iron Ore business (Sesa Goa Iron Ore), which mined more than 2 million tonnes of iron ore in 2017 and 2018, and 4 million tonnes in 2019. These numbers conflict with the figures reported by Channabasavaiah and Naidu (2021), which total 912,845 tonnes in 2018. There is a significant difference between the article's total of less than 1Mt in 2017 and Mining Data Online's over 2Mt for the Karnataka iron ore mines owned by Vedanta Resources. I would point out that this presents an opportunity for the industry to help governments improve their reporting of economic statistics in their jurisdictions. For example, there is a need for transparency in data definitions and consistency in collection. I believe private businesses can benefit when governments do a better job of measuring their economic activity and sharing it with the world.

As a further exploratory analysis, I present the estimated average number of workers per mine, based on the number of mines reported in Table 8 of Channabasavaiah and Naidu (2021). Around 100-150 people are working per day at each of 100-200 active mines. How much capital equipment is being used at these mines? How does the capital intensity of mining in India compare with other places around the world, such as iron ore mines in Australia? The Mining Data Online website sells this kind of information based on the Karnataka iron ore mines owned by Vedanta Resources.

To construct a comparable time series, I collect annual GDP per capita for Karnataka from several sources, including Pujari (2020), the Government of India, Ministry of Statistics (2012), and the Kerala State Planning Board (2016). I compare state-level GDP per capita with the total amount of mine production per mine worker to highlight a huge difference: the mining

industry is worth billions of dollars a year, yet it employs only 10,000 workers. Each worker has a significant impact.

I also combine the gross value of metal production reported by Channabasavaiah and Naidu (2021) in Table 2 with the number of workers in Table 6 to estimate the total value of all metal production per worker per year. Metal production per worker per year ranges from \$100,000 to \$200,000. Again, it is interesting to compare this with the state's GDP per capita.

Table 3	Total Mine Production in Karnataka (USD)	Number of Workers	Karnataka Mine Production Per Worker Per Year (USD)	Karnataka GDP Per Capita (USD)
Year	Table 2	Table 6	Calculated	World Bank
2008-09	\$1,211,471,835	9953	\$150,606	\$1,120
2009-10	\$1,335,577,870	10261	\$165,397	\$1,333
2010-11	\$2,138,950,757	9664	\$262,416	\$1,394
2011-12	\$893,484,700	9918	\$109,994	\$1,212
2012-13	\$1,034,844,145	8780	\$149,956	\$1,030
2013-14	\$1,261,239,056	9339	\$1,71,972	\$1,307
2014-15	\$1,234,526,528	9332	\$167,917	\$1,307
2015-16	\$837,739,395	9230	\$117,726	\$2,222
2016-17	\$1,011,987,056	9242	\$142,373	\$2,370
2017-18	\$1,439,424,960	9253	\$202,422	\$2,222
2018-19				

Mining in Karnataka is a billion-dollar industry with less than 10,000 workers. What is the labour share of income?

I do not have data on employment payments made to mine workers in Karnataka. It is possible to estimate their likely salaries relative to GDP per capita, as shown in the table above. I suppose that mine workers are paid the same amount as GDP per capita and calculate the following results.

Table 4	Total Mine Production in Karnataka (USD)	Government Royalty Total USD	Gross Payments to Workers (GDP per capita * Number of Workers)	Government Share Gross Mineral Value	Labour Share Gross Mineral Value	Remainder Share
Year	Table 2	Calculated	Calculated	Calculated	Calculated	Calculated
2008-09	\$1,211,471,835	Missing	\$11,146,872	Missing	1%	99%
2009-10	\$1,335,577,870	Missing	\$13,680,642	Missing	1%	99%
2010-11	\$2,138,950,757	Missing	\$13,470,350	Missing	1%	99%
2011-12	\$893,484,700	\$265,318,000	\$12,021,211	30%	1%	69%
2012-13	\$1,034,844,145	\$252,531,600	\$9,045,604	24%	1%	75%
2013-14	\$1,261,239,056	\$105,414,400	\$12,202,860	8%	1%	91%
2014-15	\$1,234,526,528	\$263,827,200	\$12,193,714	21%	1%	78%
2015-16	\$837,739,395	\$300,541,500	\$20,505,553	36%	2%	62%
2016-17	\$1,011,987,056	\$349,603,200	\$21,901,026	35%	2%	63%
2017-18	\$1,439,424,960	\$411,939,000	\$20,556,650	29%	1%	70%
2018-19		\$209,518,400				

When I assume each mine worker earns the same as the annual GDP per capita, the labour share of income is around 1-2% of the gross value of all mineral production. The government share ranges from 10% to 30%. The Remainder Share ranges from 60% to 99%. The Remainder Share includes the cost of capital expenditures required to sustain operations and operating costs. The Remainder Share also includes potential dividends to owners and debt service costs for all debt financing for all liabilities. The Remainder Share shows a distinct decline from 99% in 2008 to 70% in 2018.

Table 5	Total Mine Production in Karnataka (USD)	Government Royalty Total USD	Gross Payments to Workers (5x GDP per capita * Number of Workers)	Government Share Gross Mineral Value	Labour Share Gross Mineral Value	Remainder Share
Year	Table 2	Calculated	Calculated	Calculated	Calculated	Calculated
2008-09	\$1,211,471,835	Missing	\$55,734,362	Missing	5%	99%
2009-10	\$1,335,577,870	Missing	\$68,403,212	Missing	5%	99%
2010-11	\$2,138,950,757	Missing	\$67,351,750	Missing	3%	99%
2011-12	\$893,484,700	\$265,318,000	\$60,106,055	30%	7%	64%
2012-13	\$1,034,844,145	\$252,531,600	\$45,228,019	24%	4%	71%
2013-14	\$1,261,239,056	\$105,414,400	\$61,014,302	8%	5%	87%
2014-15	\$1,234,526,528	\$263,827,200	\$60,968,569	21%	5%	74%
2015-16	\$837,739,395	\$300,541,500	\$102,527,763	36%	12%	52%
2016-17	\$1,011,987,056	\$349,603,200	\$109,505,131	35%	11%	55%
2017-18	\$1,439,424,960	\$411,939,000	\$102,783,249	29%	7%	64%
2018-19		\$209,518,400				

The table assumes mine workers earn five times Karnataka's GDP per capita each year. In this hypothetical world, there are approximately 10,000 workers who each earn \$10,000 a year and account for more than 10% of the labour share of the gross value of all metal production. How do these assumptions for wages compare with real data? How does the labour share of income from mineral production vary across countries over time?

The labour share of mine workers can provide a way for indirect contributions to GDP beyond the gross value of minerals each year. For example, Table 5 above shows that mine workers in Karnataka earned \$100M in employment income in 2017, assuming each worker earns 5x GDP per capita. This assumption is made to reflect a resource boom scenario . If workers can earn relatively high wages, then they may also spend aggressively. Imagine that this group of mine workers spends 90% of their money each year on items that have a 1:1 impact on the state of Karnataka's GDP that year; this would cause an indirect increase in GDP of an additional \$90 million from the labour share of mining.

A high velocity of money could lead to an outcome where the indirect impacts on GDP

exceed the direct ones. For example, suppose there is a resource boom where mine workers earn 5x the average GDP per capita of other workers and spend 90% of their income that year. Furthermore, the mine workers' spending goes entirely into local communities with people with incomes below the GDP per capita, and those people then spend their money again immediately within the same year. At this point, the miner's income could have been paid twice, resulting in a \$180 million increase in GDP from the indirect impact of the mine workers' income and spending.

There is a direct contribution to GDP from mining through the sale of a billion dollars of iron ore each year, but the labour share may also provide indirect contributions with higher-order effects. In addition, there is potential for higher-order or multiplier effects on payments to the Remainder Share, because GDP includes dividends paid to shareholders, and the dividend recipients may further spend the money at a high velocity. The velocity of money will be slower for dividend recipients than for mine workers because of the different economic profiles of mining company shareholders and workers. Interest payments on debt are included in GDP, and there is potential for creditors to spend the interest payments they receive in a way that has high velocity of money, but generally assume banks have lower velocity of money relative to mine workers. Different ways to calculate GDP are useful for studying economic statistics for the mining industry.

GDP does include production royalty payable by mining companies to the government—different ways to calculate GDP. The government's share of GDP is calculated as total production royalties paid to the government divided by the gross metal value per producing year. Royalty rates in the tax bill around 100 Rupees in the Karnataka Legislative Assembly (2024) may seem small, but, when totalled, they amount to hundreds of millions of dollars per year.

Exploratory data analysis is functional when combining multiple different sources of data. Channabasavaiah and Naidu (2021) combined state and national data to produce different estimates of economic activity, which can be compared with other datasets. For example, Table 2 was collected from various issues of the Indian Minerals Yearbook to show the annual value of

all mineral production in Karnataka, around \$1-2 billion per year, which can be checked against other publications.

For comparison, the State Domestic Product of Karnataka for 2017 was approximately INR 13,33,240 crore. At a forex rate of 0.015 or 65 INR/USD, the total state GDP is roughly \$205 billion. Using data from Channabasavaiah and Naidu (2021), I estimate the total value of minerals at approximately \$1.4 billion, which is less than 1% of GDP.

Mining contributes to GDP in more ways than just the total value of minerals. The Government of Canada (2025) notes, “Mining accounts for 54% of the value of direct GDP contributions, followed by downstream manufacturing with 28% and primary processing with 18%.” My analysis using the Channabasavaiah and Naidu (2021) data does not capture downstream manufacturing or primary processing as potential multipliers of the GDP impacts of mining.

Also, my calculations do not include the gold mining in Karnataka. The authors mention that the state produces 3 tonnes of gold per year, valued at more than \$1 billion. This may cause the total value of metal production to exceed 1% of GDP and raise further questions about the labour share of income associated with gold mining.

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